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The official congress committee of The 2nd European Congress of Health Sciences (ECHS) consists of medical doctors working independently, and Aydan Çevik Varol MD, Assist. Prof. of Family Medicine working as a state university staff at Namik Kemal University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Family Medicine, Tekirdag, Turkiye. This statement is placed here to declare that ECHS meets the UAK associate professorship application criteria in Turkey.

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The Importance of Human Resource Management in Nursing

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ABSTRACT

The healthcare sector is constantly evolving, facing the challenge of adapting to the continuous emergence of new diseases, treatments, and methods of prevention and health promotion. It is a sector where there is competition to provide rapid and effective care to a population increasingly seeking health education and their rights in general. In this dynamic and complex sector, the most valuable resource for organizations is undoubtedly the qualified healthcare professional. There are several professional groups working in healthcare institutions that must coordinate to provide assistance to patients and the community. However, among these professional groups, nursing stands out as the most representative, constantly by the patients' side. The aim of this theoretical reflection was to emphasize the importance of human resource management in the nursing field. This reflection was based on reading, analysis, and interpretation of scientific texts found in diverse databases. The continuity of nursing care is crucial for patient safety, highlighting the need for efficient human resource management. Workforce planning, recruitment and selection, compensation and benefits management, training and development, performance management, and team relationship management are some of the activities involved in human resource management. When human resource management in nursing is carried out adequately, nurses work with greater satisfaction, and the quality of care increases, as well-managed human resources lead to equity, autonomy, and competence, promoting healthy interpersonal interactions. On the other hand, failures in this process can result in staff shortages, absenteeism, high turnover, errors in practice, and lack of commitment to the profession, compromising the well-being of the nursing team and the quality of care. It is, therefore, evident that administrators of healthcare institutions and nurse managers play crucial roles in the development and maintenance of effective and efficient human resource management processes in the nursing field.

Keywords: Health management, human resource, nurse administrators, nursing, quality of health care nursing